

Evaluation of Volatile Solids (VS) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) in Continuous Anaerobic Digestion of Selected Agro-Wastes

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Abstract: The increasing demand for renewable energy and sustainable waste management has led to growing interest in the anaerobic digestion (AD) of agro-wastes. This study evaluates the changes in Volatile Solids (VS) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) during the continuous anaerobic digestion of four selected agro-waste substrates: Cassava Peels (CP), Maize Husks (MH), Pig Slurry (PS), and a Composite Mixture (CM). The substrates were monitored over a 45-day digestion period to assess their degradation characteristics and potential for biogas generation. Results showed minimal fluctuations in VS values across the digestion period, indicating a steady degradation process. Cassava peels maintained a VS value of 3.38 g/L at 24 hours and day 30, with a slight increase to 3.43 g/L at day 45. Maize husks consistently exhibited the highest VS values, peaking at 3.93 g/L by day 45. BOD values, however, varied more significantly, reflecting the dynamic microbial activity during digestion. A general decrease in BOD was observed by day 30, followed by a rise by day 45, suggesting renewed microbial breakdown of complex organics. The composite substrate (CM) showed stable and high BOD values throughout, peaking at 80.00 mg/L by day 45, indicating a synergistic effect in substrate combination. This study highlights the relevance of VS and BOD as critical indicators in assessing the efficiency and stability of continuous anaerobic digestion. The findings support the potential of these agro-wastes, especially composite mixtures, for sustainable bioenergy production and organic waste management.

Keywords: Anaerobic Digestion, Biogas Production, Agro-wastes, Renewable Energy, Circular

Introduction

The global drive towards sustainable energy and environmental protection has intensified interest in the valorization of organic waste, particularly through anaerobic digestion (US DOE, 2020). Anaerobic digestion, a microbial process that breaks down organic matter in the absence of oxygen, has proven to be an effective method for producing biogas while simultaneously treating waste and reducing environmental pollution. Agro-wastes, generated in large quantities from agricultural and food-processing activities, represent a significant and underutilized resource in this context. Their high organic content makes them ideal feedstocks for biogas production, contributing not only to energy recovery but also to waste minimization and soil enrichment through the resultant digestate (US EPA, 2013).

Effective monitoring and optimization of anaerobic digestion rely heavily on key parameters such as Volatile Solids (VS) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD). VS provides a measure of the organic matter available for microbial degradation, serving as a proxy for potential biogas yield (Aichinger, 2015). BOD reflects the oxygen demand of biodegradable organics and serves as an indicator of the substrate's pollution load and biodegradability (Hill &

Bolte, 2019). These parameters are crucial in evaluating the efficiency, stability, and environmental sustainability of the digestion process, particularly in continuous systems that mimic real-world operations.

This study investigates the behavior of VS and BOD in the continuous anaerobic digestion of selected agro-wastes. By examining the degradation dynamics of these parameters over time, the research aims to provide insights into the efficiency of the digestion process and the suitability of the chosen feedstocks. The findings are expected to inform best practices for agro-waste management and enhance the design of sustainable bioenergy systems, especially in agricultural economies seeking renewable energy alternatives.

Material and Methods

Sample collection

The agro-waste samples used in this study were collected using standard procedures of APHA (2015), to ensure consistency and representativeness. They were sourced from local village households at Obinze (the study location). Cassava peels (CP) collection was done immediately after peeling during cassava processing activities. The peels were gathered in clean, labeled polyethylene bags to prevent contamination and transported promptly to the laboratory

for processing. The maize husks (MH) were collected post-harvest, ensuring they were free from mold and other visible contaminants. They were bagged in clean sacks and stored under dry conditions prior to laboratory analysis.

Pig slurry (PS) was sampled from the mid-layer of the slurry pit using a sterilized scoop to obtain a representative mixture of solids and liquids (Lee et al., 2020). Samples were placed in airtight, labeled containers and transported to the research location under cool conditions to preserve microbial integrity.

All samples were processed within 24 hours of collection. The composite (CM) sample was prepared by mixing equal portions of CP, MH, and PS on a wet weight basis. Each sample was homogenized and pre-treated as necessary before loading into the continuous anaerobic digester setup. The collection methods complied with standard biosafety and environmental guidelines to ensure data reliability and reproducibility.

Sample Treatment

Standard procedures were employed in treating the agro-waste samples to enhance uniformity and digestion efficiency. Cassava peels (CP) and maize husks (MH) were first washed with clean water to remove dirt and extraneous materials. They were then

shredded into tiny particles using a mechanical grater to increase surface area and improve microbial access during digestion. The shredded materials were weighed and stored in clean containers prior to use.

Pig slurry was homogenized by thorough stirring to ensure uniform distribution of solids and liquids (Ighravwe & Babatunde, 2018). Large debris or foreign materials were removed by sieving through a 2 mm mesh. Equal portions of the treated samples (CP, MH, and homogenized PS), were mixed to obtain the composite (CM). All samples were kept at ambient temperature and used within 24 hours of preparation to preserve freshness and microbial activity.

Proximate and Physicochemical Analysis

The agro-waste samples underwent proximate and physicochemical analysis according to the AOAC methods (2012), to evaluate their biodegradability and energy potential for anaerobic digestion. Special emphasis was placed on volatile solids (VS) and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), as they are key indicators of organic load and microbial activity.

VS was determined gravimetrically by first drying the samples at 105 °C to obtain total solids (TS), followed by ignition at 550 °C in a muffle furnace to estimate the organic

fraction. This provided a measure of the biodegradable portion available for microbial breakdown.

BOD was assessed using the 5-day BOD test (BOD₅), which measures the amount of oxygen consumed by aerobic microorganisms during the decomposition of organic matter. This test reflects the strength of the waste and its potential impact on the environment.

pH was recorded using a digital pH meter, other parameters, such as moisture and ash content, were also analyzed using standard AOAC (2012) methods to support overall substrate characterization.

Bacterial Analysis and Characterization

Bacterial analysis was carried out to identify and characterize the microbial communities involved in the anaerobic digestion process. Samples were collected from the digesters at different retention times and serially diluted using sterile distilled water. The diluted samples were cultured on nutrient, Salmonella-Shigella and Chromogenic agar plates, using the pour plate technique and incubated at 37 °C for 24-48 hours.

Distinct bacterial colonies were counted to determine colony-forming units (CFU/mL) and sub-cultured for purification. Pure isolates were subjected to morphological

characterization through Gram staining and microscopic observation (Cheesbrough, 2010).

Further biochemical characterization was conducted using standard tests such as catalase, oxidase, citrate utilization, indole production, and sugar fermentation tests, following protocols outlined by Cheesbrough (2010). The results were compared with Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology for identification.

This analysis provided insight into the dominant bacterial species responsible for organic matter breakdown and biogas production during digestion.

Design of Used Digesters

The four-compartment digester shown was designed for continuous fermentation, using a modified method of Ugwu et al. (2021). It comprises a linear arrangement of four connected metallic chambers, each allowing staged microbial activity. Substrates are first introduced to the second chamber. Subsequently, new substrates move to the second chamber through the first one, while spent medium is released to the third/fourth chamber for retention or evacuation. This setup ensures uninterrupted feedstock input and simultaneous removal of digested

effluent. The design promotes gradual fermentation, optimal retention time, and consistent biogas production. Its metal structure enhances durability, while the open access allows monitoring and maintenance at each stage. The configuration supports efficient conversion of organic matter and is suitable for both pilot and field-scale bio-conversion studies (Zang et al., 2024).

Plate 1 A four step digester used for the continuous fermentation

Sample Feeding

For each 30L capacity digester, approximately 20L (2/3 of total volume) was initially loaded with feedstock, leaving 10L headspace for gas accumulation. The feeding followed a continuous method where 2.5L of fresh substrate was added daily. Before each substrate feeding, an

equivalent volume of the spent digestate was removed to maintain a constant working volume. This daily interval feeding allowed for a balanced microbial activity, steady biogas production, and minimized system shock (Das & Mondal, 2023). The substrates were homogenized and manually introduced through the inlet ports, ensuring uniform distribution across the chambers. Daily stirring (of 2 minutes) was achieved by a mechanical agitator. This approach supported retention time, process stability, and maintained anaerobic conditions throughout the digestion period.

Gas Sampling and Volume Measurement

Biogas sampling and volume measurement followed standard procedures outlined by Garfi et al. (2021), to ensure accuracy and safety. Gas was collected daily (from day 20), using water displacement method with a calibrated gas collection chamber. The displaced water volume was recorded as the gas volume generated. This method minimized contamination and allowed for visual monitoring of gas production rates. For flammability testing, a small portion of the collected gas was released and ignited using a gas burner directly connected to the digesters. A steady blue flame indicated the presence of methane-rich biogas (Nwankwo, 2014). Gas sampling for analysis was done using gas-tight syringes or Tedlar bags, ensuring no atmospheric interference. To

maintain consistency, all measurements were conducted at room temperature and atmospheric pressure, with necessary adjustments for standard temperature and pressure (STP) conditions. These methods provided reliable estimates of biogas yield and quality, essential for evaluating the performance of the digester and the suitability of the feedstock for anaerobic digestion (Pham et al., 2013).

Plate 2 Gas flammability testing, using gas burner directly connected to a digester

Results and Discussions

Proximate analysis result

Ash content, a measure of inorganic matter, ranged from 1.89 % to 3.50 %, with an average of 2.74 %. Maize husks had a higher ash content, compared to others. According to Ubalua (2017), this suggests that it contain more inorganic components. Also, it had higher carbon content (a measure of organic matter) of 6.38 %, an indication that it is rich in organic matter (Sharma, 2010).

Crude fibre, a measure of indigestible plant material, ranged from 1.39 to 3.98 %, with an average of 2.83 %. Cassava peel and maize husks had higher fiber content, compared to pig slurry and the composite. Al-Seadi and Holm-Nielsen (2022) attributed high fiber content to richness in cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. However, crude fat was low across all samples, with pig slurry recording the highest average of 3.40 %. This, according to Macias-Corral et al. (2008) and Speece (2016), is attributed to the presence of lipids from animal waste in pig slurry. The same is applicable to protein content.

Table 1 Proximate values of sample contents at 24hrs of setup

PARAMETERS	CP	MH	PS	CM
Ash (%)	2.79 ±0.17	3.50 ±0.22	1.89 ±0.12	2.79 ±0.17
Moisture (%)	84.56 ±5.28	80.24 ±5.01	81.94 ±5.12	82.70 ±5.16
Crude Fibre (%)	3.47 ±0.22	3.98 ±0.25	1.39 ±0.09	2.48 ±0.15
Crude Fat (%)	1.20 ±0.07	2.05 ±0.13	3.40 ±0.21	2.20 ±0.14
Protein (%)	1.52 ±0.9	3.09 ±0.19	4.51 ±0.28	3.03 ±0.19
Carbon (%)	4.69 ±0.20	6.38 ±0.28	3.91 ±0.17	4.79 ±0.21

Values are means of duplicate determinations with standard deviations (Mean±SD). CP = Cassava CP = Cassava Peel, MH = Maize husks, PS = Pig Slurry, CM = Composite.

Physicochemical Characteristics of the Agro-waste Substrates

The results of this study showed that pig slurry had the highest initial pH value. Singh and Sooch (2014) attributed it to the significant amount of ammonia, primarily derived from the breakdown of nitrogen-containing compounds in pig waste. Ammonia is a weak base that can

contribute to the alkalinity of the slurry when it reacts with water. Urine and other nitrogenous waste in pig slurry contain urea, which can undergo hydrolysis, leading to the release of ammonia. This process contributes to the overall alkalinity of the slurry (Vesilind, 2016). The high pH in the composite was contributed by the pig slurry.

Table 2. Physicochemical Properties of Sample Contents at 24hrs of Setup

PARAMETERS	CP	MH	PS	CM
TS (%)	10.68 ±0.67	11.37 ±0.71	12.75 ±0.80	10.65 ±0.67
VS (%)	3.38 ±0.21	3.86 ±0.24	3.45 ±0.22	3.57 ±0.22
COD (mg/L)	219.2 ±13.69	192.0 ±11.99	234.4 ±14.64	219.2 ±13.69
BOD (mg/L)	73.60 ±4.60	73.60 ±4.60	73.60 ±4.60	73.60 ±4.60
pH	7.71 ±0.48	9.81 ±0.61	11.51 ±0.72	9.52 ±0.59

Values are means of duplicate determinations with standard deviations (Mean±SD).

CP = Cassava Peel, MH = Maize husks, PS = Pig Slurry, CM = Composite.

Microscopic and Biochemical Characteristics of Bacteria Isolates

Table 3 presents a comprehensive analysis of various bacteria isolates based on their microscopic and biochemical characteristics. Isolates were obtained from the four (4) different substrates. This result is crucial for understanding the microbial dynamics in substrates, as related to biogas production, -which relies heavily on the activities of diverse microbial consortium to convert organic matters into biogas, primarily methane and carbon dioxide. *Staphylococcus* sp, *E. faecalis*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Bacillus subtilis* were found in all the substrates. *Shigella* sp. and *Salmonella* sp. were present in samples MH,

PS, and CM, while *Serratia* sp. was only present in PS, and CM.

Prescott et al. (2015) established that wastes can harbour a diverse array of microbes, including bacteria, fungi, viruses, etc. These microbes can be either beneficial, such as those involved in organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling, and/or potentially harmful, including pathogens that can pose risks to human health and the environment. This claim is validated in the results obtained, where pathogens like *Shigella dysenteriae*, *B. subtilis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, were identified in the substrates. These bacteria have been implicated to cause foodborne illnesses, diarrhea, and abdominal cramps by Bassani et al. (2015).

Table 3 Microscopic and biochemical characteristics of bacteria isolates

Gram Rxn	Spo	Mot	Oxi	Cat	Coag	In	MR	VP	CU	S	L	G	M	Identity of Isolates	Substrate involved
-R	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	CP,PS,CM
-R	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	MH,PS,CM
-R	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	MH,PS,CM
+R	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	CP,MH,PS,CM
+S	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	CP,MH,PS,CM
+R	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	CP,MH,PS,CM
+R	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	CP,MH,PS,CM
-R	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	CP,PS,CM
-R	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Serratia marcesens</i>	PS,CM

Gram negative (-R), Gram positive (+R), Spore Forming (+S), Reaction (rxn), Spore (Spo), Motile (Mot), Oxidase (Oxi), Catalase (Cat), Coagulase (Coag), Indole (In), Methyl Red (MR), Voges-Proskauer, Citrate Utilization (CU), Sucrose (S), Lactose (L), Glucose (G), Mannitol (M), negative (-), positive (+), Cassava peel (CP), Maize husk (MH), Pig slurry (PS), Composite (CM).

Percentage Values of Methane (CH₄) and Carbondioxide (CO₂) Present in the Generated Biogas

The variation between methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) production during anaerobic digestion is a key indicator of the efficiency and stability of the process (Nges et al. (2015). Table 4 shows that an increase in one is almost inversely proportional to a decrease in the other. Methane values ranged from 57.992±3.62 (for CP) to 83.946±5.24 (for CM), indicating

variability in the total methane production among the substrates. The result suggests that co-digestion of substrates is more effective in harnessing methane for energy generation.

Codigestion, the process of digesting multiple substrates together (composite), often results in a higher gas yield compared to monodigestion, where a single substrate is used (Yang & Li, 2014). Results proved that the composite, an equal combination of cassava peels, maize husks, and pig slurry,

co-digested together yielded the highest gas amongst others. From the result, one can conclude that continuous fermentation and co-digestion are necessary to maximize biogas yield in anaerobic fermentation. According to UN Energy Report (2015), the combination of different substrates in co-digestion can result in synergistic

degradation, where certain compounds in one substrate can facilitate the breakdown of complex components in another. This synergistic effect enhances the overall degradation efficiency, leading to increased gas production from the combined substrates.

Table 4 Percentage Values of Methane (CH₄) and Carbondioxide (CO₂) Present in the Generated Biogas, for Continuous Fermentation.

CONTENTS	CP	MH	PS	CM
Methane (%)	57.992 ±3.62	71.107 ±4.44	79.468 ±4.96	83.946 ±5.24
CO ₂ (%)	36.636 ±1.60	25.383 ±1.11	16.426 ±0.72	13.847 ±0.60

Values are means of duplicate determinations with standard deviations (Mean±SD). CP = Cassava Peel, MH = Maize husks, PS = Pig Slurry, CM = Composite.

Volatile Solid (VS) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) of Digester Contents, for Continuous Digestion.

VS concentrations remained relatively stable in all samples over the 45-day period, with slight fluctuation, indicating a consistent breakdown of organic matter. At 24 hours, VS ranges from 3.38 to 3.86. By day 45, these values are slightly higher, ranging from 3.43 to 3.93. Notably, maize husks recorded the highest VS values throughout (3.86-3.93%), suggesting a greater amount of degradable organic matter. In contrast, cassava peels and pig slurry showed marginal increases in VS by

day 45, while the composite peaked at 3.62%. The relative stability was as a result of the continuous feeding of feedstocks and removal of spent media (Kamalinasab et al., 2016).

Initial BOD values at 24 hours are uniformly high across all substrates at 73.60 mg/L, indicating similar organic loadings. By day 30, maize husks experienced the most substantial BOD reduction (57.6 mg/L), reflecting active biodegradation and possibly more efficient microbial utilization of organic substrates. Interestingly, by day 45, BOD values rebound and increased significantly for all

substrates, reaching between 78.40 mg/L and 83.20 mg/L. This was as a result of continued high level of microbial activities

and the sustained presence of degradable feedstocks (Khalid et al., 2011).

Table 5 Volatile Solid (VS) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) of Digester Contents, for Continuous Digestion.

PARAMETERS	CP	MH	PS	CM
VS (at 24 hrs)	3.38 ±0.15	3.86 ±0.18	3.45 ±0.15	3.57 ±0.16
VS (day 30)	3.38 ±0.12	3.86 ±0.16	3.45 ±0.11	3.57 ±0.10
VS (day 45)	3.43 ±0.15	3.93 ±0.19	3.50 ±0.16	3.62 ±0.17
BOD (at 24 hrs)	73.60 ±3.21	73.60 ±3.21	73.60 ±2.21	73.60 ±3.21
BOD (day 30)	65.6 ±4.10	57.6 ±3.60	70.4 ±4.40	65.6 ±4.10
BOD (day 45)	80.00 ±3.49	83.20 ±3.63	78.40 ±3.42	80.00 ±3.49

Values are means of duplicate determinations with standard deviations (Mean±SD). VS (%), BOD (mg/L). CP = Cassava Peel, MH = Maize husks, PS = Pig Slurry, CM = Composite.

Conclusion

This research characterized the continuous digestion process by evaluating volatile solids (VS) and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD). While VS remained largely consistent, indicating a sustained organic load, BOD exhibited dynamic changes. The initial high BOD, followed by a decrease, and then a rebound, suggests complex microbial activity and sequential degradation of organic matter (Chen et al., 2018). These findings highlight the variable nature of substrate utilization in continuous

digestion, providing crucial insights for optimizing waste treatment and resource recovery.

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References

- Aichinger, P. (2015). Synergistic co-digestion of solid-organic-waste and municipal-sewage-sludge: 1 plus 1 equals more than 2 in terms of biogas production and solids reduction. *Water Resources*, 87, 416-423.
- Al-Seadi, T. & Holm Nielsen J. (2022). Utilisation of waste from food and agriculture: Solid waste: Assesment, Monitoring and Remediation; *Waste management series 4*; ELSEVIER; ISBN 0080443214, 735-754.
- American Public Health Association-APHA (2015). *Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater*, Washington DC, USA, pp. 22-24.
- AOAC, (2012). Official Method of Analysis: *Association of Analytical Chemists*. 19th Edition, Washington DC, 121-130.
- Bassani, I., Kougiyas, P. G., Treu, L. & Angelidaki, I. (2015). Biogas upgrading via hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis in two-stage Continuous Stirred Tank Reactors at mesophilic and thermophilic conditions. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 49, 585-593.
- Cheesbrough, M. (2010). *District laboratory practice in tropical countries*. 2nd Edition, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom. 101-125.
- Chen, Y., Cheng, J.J, Creamer, K.S. (2018). Inhibition of anaerobic process, a review. *Bioresour Technol.* 99, 4044–4064.
- Das, A. & Mondal. C. (2023). Kinetic Study of Biogas production from mixed Fruit and Vegetable Waste. *International Journal of Engineering Sciences and Research Technology*, 2(10), 2646-2656.
- Garfi, M., Ferrer-Marti, L., Villegas, V., & Ferrer, I. (2021). Psychrophilic anaerobic digestion of guinea pig manure in low-cost tubular digesters at high altitude. *Bioresource Technology*, 102 (10), 6356-6359.
- Hill, D. J. & Bolte, J. P. (2019). Synthetic fixed media reactor performance treating screened swine waste liquids. *Biofuel Energies*, 31, 1525-1531.
- Ighravwe, D. E. & Babatunde, M. O. (2018). Determination of a suitable renewable energy source for mini-grid business: A risk-based multicriteria Approach. *Journal of Renewable Energy*, 20: 50-61.

- Kamalinasab, M., Vakili, A., Danesh-Mesgaran, M., Valizadeh, R. & Nabavi, S. R. (2016). Modelling anaerobic digestion of cow manure to predict methane flow rate. *Iranian Journal of Applied Animal Science*, 6(3), 525-533.
- Khalid, A., Arshad, M., Anjum, M., Mahmood, T. & Dawson, L. (2011). anaerobic digestion of solid organic waste. *Waste Management*, 31, 1737-1744.
- Kim, J., Park, C., Kim, T. H., Lee, M., Kim, S., Kim, S. W. & Lee, J. (2013). Effects of various pretreatments for enhanced anaerobic digestion with waste activated sludge. *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*, 95(3), 271-275.
- Lee, Y., Chung, Y. C. & Jung, J. Y. (2020). Effects of chemical and enzymatic treatments on the hydrolysis of swine waste water. *Water and Science Technology*, 58(7), 1529-1534.
- Macias-Corral. M., Samani, Z., Hanson, A., Smith, G., Funk, P, Yu, H. & Longworth J. (2008). Anaerobic digestion of municipal solid waste and agricultural waste and the effect of co-digestion with dairy cow manure. *Bioresource Technology*, 9, 288-293.
- Nges, I. A., Lovisa, B. & Hinrich, U. (2015). Anaerobic digestion of crop and waste biomass: *Impact of Feedstock Characteristics on Process Performance*. Denmark: Lund University, pp. 105-125.
- Nwanko, J. I. (2014). Production of biogas from paper waste blended with cow dung. *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology, and Food Technology*, 8(10), 58-68.
- Pham, C. H., Triolo, J. M., Cu, T. T. T., Pedersen, L. & Sommer, S. G. (2013). Validation and recommendation of methods to measure biogas production potential of animal manure. *Australian Journal of Animal Science*, 18, 17-26.
- Prescott, L. M., Harley, J. P. & Klein, D.A. (2015). *Microbiology*. Sixth International Edition. Mcgraw-Hill Publishing Company, UK, 652-668.
- Sharma, N. (2010). Isolation and characterization of some hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria, isolated from contaminated soil in Zuma, Bwari Area Council, FCT, Abuja, Nigeria. *Microbiology*

- Research Journal International*, 22(6),1-8.
- Singh, K. J. & Sooch, S. S. (2014). Comparative study of economics of different models of family size biogas plants for state of Punjab, India. *Energy Conversion Management*, 45, 1329-1341.
- Speece, R. E. (2016). *Anaerobic Biotechnology and Odour/Corrosion Control – for Municipalities and Industries*, Archae Press, Nashville. Pp. 49-53.
- Ubalua A. O. (2017). Cassava wastes: treatment options and value addition alternative. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 6(18), 2065-73.
- Ugwu, T. N., Nwachukwu, A. A., Ogbulie, T. E. & Anyalogbu E. A. (2021). Compositional assessment of selected plant-based substrates for biogas production. *Journal of Advances in Biology & Biotechnology*, 24(3),1-6.
- UN Energy Report, (2015). Energy for a sustainable future: Summary report and recommendations from the Advisory Group on Energy and Climate Change (AGECC). Pp. 542-602
- US DOE, (2020). United States Department of Energy’s Bioenergy Research Centers: An overview of the science, DOE/SC-0127. Office of Biological and Environmental Research within the DOE office of science. Pp. 44-52. Available on genomicscience.energy.gov/centers/rbrcbrochure.pdf. Retrieved May. 10th, 2025.
- US EPA. (2013). Environmental regulations and technology: Control of pathogens and vector attraction in sewage sludge under CFR part 503. Report No. 625/R-92/013. Cincinnati, OH: US EPA. Pp.104-115.
- Vesilind, P. A. (2016). Wastewater treatment plant design (4th ed.). London, UK and Alexandria, VA, USA: *IWA Publishing*. Pp. 100-121.
- Yang, L. & Li, Y. (2014). Anaerobic digestion of giant reed for methane production. *Bioresource Technology*, 171, 233-239.
- Zhang, C., Xiao, G., Peng, L., Su, H. & Tan, T. (2024). The anaerobic co-digestion of food waste and cattle manure. *Bioresource Technology*, 129(1), 170-17